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Dynamics of the Patron-Client Relationship and the Resolution of Frozen Conflicts: The Case of Nagorno-Karabakh

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ABSTRACT

In October 2023, following a surprise military operation conducted by Azeri forces, the frozen conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh became the first of its kind to be brought to an end within the post-Soviet space. Given that the Russian Federation played a prominent role in this conflict even from its emergence, any consideration of its termination should take into account the interests of the Russian Federation as shaped by the war in Ukraine. Therefore, an explanation for the violent conclusion of the Nagorno-Karabakh frozen conflict is advanced in this paper by framing the Russian approach to it in terms of the theory of the patron-client relationship as adapted to secessionist frozen conflicts. The findings are given a broader formulation that could bear relevance for other frozen conflicts around the Black Sea.

Keywords: Nagorno-Karabakh, secessionist frozen conflict, patron-client relationship, post-Soviet space, Russian Federation, South Caucasus, Azerbaijan, Armenia

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Since the dissolution of the Soviet Union, frozen conflicts have emerged as a source of insecurity in the Black Sea Region and in all of them, the strategy of the Russian Federation to exert significant influence in the post-Soviet space was highly visible. When the aggression against Ukraine was launched in February 2022, such conflicts already existed in Transnistria, South Ossetia, Abkhazia, Nagorno-Karabakh and, according to some experts, also in Donbas (Eastern Ukraine)¹. During the war in Ukraine, the frozen conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh, which had long antagonised Azerbaijan and Armenia, ended following a surprising military action undertaken in 2023 by Azeri forces. This paper aims to apply a theoretical framework that could provide an explanation for the cessation of this frozen conflict and to this purpose it proceeds by first analysing the state of play in academic literature on the definition of frozen conflicts. Building on definitional aspects shared among various scholars, the paper further relies on the theory of the patron-client relationship to explore the dynamics of third-party involvement in secessionist frozen conflicts. The third strand of the paper consists in using the theory of the patron-client relationship for considering the international dimension of the frozen conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh, particularly the role assumed therein by the Russian Federation and its underpinning rationales that developed against the background of the war in Ukraine. The paper concludes by assessing the adequacy for the conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh of both the definitional elements generally associated with frozen conflicts and the central tenets of the patron-client relationship. Moreover,

from the circumstances which determined the Russian Federation to act for the termination of the frozen conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh, general conditions are abstracted that could bear influence on the policy pursued by the Russian Federation in relation to other frozen conflicts near the Black Sea.

Revolving around the question *Why has the frozen conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh terminated?*, the research approach developed in this article is primarily explanatory and relies on a qualitative methodology built upon an individual case study designed to apply a theory.

A theoretical background for the patron-client relationship in the context of secessionist frozen conflicts

Despite its frequency in academic literature, the theoretical consideration of the term *frozen conflict* is still developing² and it is expected that more conceptual clarity will eventually emerge. It is argued that, prior to the end of the Cold War, the term *frozen conflict* was absent from the field of international relations and had low currency in other domains, with psychology and psychiatry being its primary areas of use³. According to this reading, only in the 1990s did this term gradually begin to be used in connection with international affairs issues, namely with conflicts arising in states that had recently emerged from the dissolution of the Soviet Union⁴. However, attempts to formulate a definition of the concept are to be found even in the 1960s when Kalevi Holsti brought its contribution in this direction⁵. Holsti defines international conflicts as the existence of incompatible objectives held by two or more states and pursued by them through the effective use of force or the threat to resort to force⁶. He highlights the distinctiveness of frozen conflicts by contrasting them with passive settlement as a means of resolving conflicts. Thus, Holsti indicates that parties involved in a conflict reach a resolution through passive settlement when their commitment to those objectives underpinning their conflictual rela-

tionship diminishes over time and makes them to implicitly accept the existing *status quo* (e.g. the conflict between the Soviet Union and the United States over the division of Korea)⁷. In the case of frozen conflicts, the commitment of the parties to the objectives grounding their colliding positions does not diminish so that, even in the long run, the conflict is not heading towards a resolution (e.g. the issues of the German reunification and of Kashmir)⁸; consequently, the use of force or the threat of force could be said to be always looming in the case of a frozen conflict. It is also to be observed that, for Holsti, the freezing of a conflict is different not only from passive settlement but also from any other form of resolution, including military defeat (conquest), which means that parties to a frozen conflict are not engaged in an effort to resolve it but simply avoid, for the time being, to engage in any possible way of solving their differences. Taking into account that, for Holsti, an international conflict does not always imply the recourse to force, it means that frozen conflicts are not conceived by him as necessarily following from an armed conflict. Moreover, Holsti acknowledges that rebellion within a state aiming at secessionist objectives is a form of international territorial conflict when rebels and/or the government they fight against benefit from outside support⁹; consequently, it could be argued that it accords with his view to consider that frozen conflicts could also develop under such circumstances.

The definition provided for frozen conflicts by Holsti is generally absent from literature reviews of this topic¹⁰ where the theoretical contribution from 2009 by Valery Perry is indicated as an early attempt to consider the meaning of the concept¹¹. Elaborating on this suggestion, one could remark that Perry holds the view that a frozen conflict follows the cessation of an inconclusive armed conflict and it also implies the commitment to opposing interests that led up to violence does not decrease over time and is not seriously dealt with¹²; it follows that she does not regard a frozen conflict as a form of conflict resolution. On these grounds, Perry argues that frozen conflicts underpin only an imperfect peace. Moreover, Perry indicates that there are cases where the existence of a frozen conflict is made

possible by the involvement of external parties which constantly act to prevent the resurgence of violence. Given that Perry advanced her definition in relation to the situation in Bosnia and Herzegovina where she considered that secessionist objectives represented a threat to the existence of the state, her understanding of frozen conflicts implicitly addresses the interplay between external parties and supporters of secession.

Another definition was put forward in 2019 by Michal Smetana and Jan Ludvík who argue that a frozen conflict presupposes an international armed conflict that came to a halt and turned into a protracted conflict; a frozen conflict is, therefore, a peculiar type of protracted conflict that emerges in the aftermath of a war¹³. The two authors maintain that the dispute fuelling such a conflict remains ongoing and involves highly prominent issues for the parties involved so that the existing peace is just an unstable one which could easily give place to violence. Smetana and Ludvík indicate that the international character of a frozen conflict is present even when it takes place between a state and a state-like entity formed on its territory and which assumes state attributes (a *de facto* state) – including the possession of conventional armed forces – and which normally depends on a patronising external power¹⁴.

A definition of frozen conflicts was compiled in 2022 by Adriana Cuppuleri who indicates that they emerge after the cessation of an international armed conflict, usually, between a state enjoying international recognition and a *de facto* state from within its internationally recognised borders that claims therein territory, rights and independence for ethnic groups, and that the cessation of hostilities, not being grounded on a peace treaty, is an unstable one¹⁵. She also points out that the divergent interests of the parties to the conflict are constantly kept at high intensity. These features, Cuppuleri indicates, distinguish frozen conflicts from the peace process so that a frozen conflict should not be brought under the scope of conflict resolution¹⁶.

A comparative analysis of these definitions points out that there are significant similarities between them: the persistence of a high level of commitment to their objectives evinced by

the parties to the conflict, the possibility of secessionists to be party to the conflict, the risk of the outbreak of violence which makes peace unstable, the involvement of external powers. With the exception of Holsti, it is considered that frozen conflicts necessarily follow an armed conflict.

The definitions by Perry, Smetana and Ludvík, and Cuppuleri are intended to cover frozen conflicts as a phenomenon that is not confined to the territory of the former Soviet Union, albeit they are ordinarily associated with this geographic area¹⁷; it is to be mentioned that the conflicts in Abkhazia, South Ossetia, Transnistria and Nagorno-Karabakh are all regarded by Smetana, Ludvík and Cuppuleri as frozen conflicts from the former Soviet space. The broad geographical scope attributed to the definition of this concept is also obvious in the case of Holsti who considered it long before the dissolution of the Soviet Union. This comprehensive understanding makes it possible for present or past conflicts in various parts of the world to be ranked as frozen, e.g. Bosnia and Herzegovina after the signing of the Dayton Agreement¹⁸, Kosovo¹⁹, Northern Cyprus²⁰, Western Sahara²¹, Syria²², Korean Peninsula²³, Taiwan²⁴. It is telling in this respect that, applying to the period 1946-2011 the definition advanced by Smetana and Ludvík, a total number of 42 frozen conflicts have been identified, of which 17 opposed a state to a *de facto* state²⁵.

A narrower definition of frozen conflicts was put forward in 2017 by Thomas D. Grant who, considering that the conflicts in Transnistria, Nagorno-Karabakh, South Ossetia, and Abkhazia, all located in the former Soviet area, are archetypal frozen conflicts, argued that the definition of a frozen conflict should be built upon the characteristics of these conflicts²⁶. Consequently, he lists its following constitutive elements: the parties are a state and the separatists from its own territory who fight for self-determination with support from an external actor; following an armed conflict with the state, separatists have acquired control over part of the state's territory and have established therein a *de facto* state of their own which lacks any international recognition; the internal frontiers resulting

from the conflict are relatively stable for being grounded on juridical settlements, but the risk of renewed violence is always present; third parties are only occasionally and inconclusively involved in the resolution of the conflict. A relevant characteristic of this definition is that frozen conflicts develop exclusively between a state and a *de facto* state within its territory, an entity defined by Grant as lacking any international recognition of its independence. Another specificity of Grant's definition is that external powers are involved only on behalf of the *de facto* state. His account of frozen conflicts takes on from the definitions considered above the following elements: the preexistence of an armed conflict, the parties' high level of commitment to their opposed objectives, the status of secessionists as a party to the conflict, the continuous possibility for violence to re-emerge, the involvement of external powers. With respect to the first element, it is to be observed that it does not explicitly exclude the possibility for other armed conflicts to exist during the lifespan of a frozen conflict²⁷ albeit its tacit assumption seems to be that only its starting point is marked by an armed conflict.

It should be noted that the definitions under review do not convey the idea that the freezing of a conflict means it is petrified, or it lacks dynamics, and, consequently, these definitions evade the frequent objection brought to the concept of a frozen conflict on the grounds that it erroneously portrays conflicts as being static and thus as capable to remain virtually unchanged until a resolution is worked out²⁸. It is maintained that the dynamics of a frozen conflict encompass process such as the development of a political identity among separatists²⁹, their relationship with the host state³⁰ and third parties, including patron state(s), the interactions between the host state and third parties³¹.

The analysis will further concentrate on one aspect of the dynamics of frozen conflicts that figures in all definitions previously analysed, namely the involvement of external powers. Equally, because the paper focuses on the conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh, the role played by external powers will be considered against the background of frozen conflicts of a secessionist nature.

The presence of external powers in frozen conflicts with a secessionist underpinning could be adequately framed through the theoretical approach of the patron-client relationship. However, as argued by Rafael Biermann, there are currently serious shortcomings in the research on patron-client relationships within the context of conflicts serving secessionist objectives³². Biermann indicates that the study of how support by patrons influences secessionist conflicts addresses in an inconclusive manner the support to a host state provided by its patron, the rivalry between patrons of the host state and of the secessionists, and the cessation of a patron-client relationship³³. Biermann identifies four characteristics of the patron-client relationship³⁴: (1) it represents a partnership for tangible or/and intangible resource exchange that is voluntarily established and maintained by both sides; (2) it is grounded on an asymmetric power dependence in favour of the patron; (3) it entails flexibility resulting from various degrees of diffusion that inform the mutual obligations formally or informally assumed by both parties; (4) it is set up for a long period of time. He emphasises that, for an international actor to count as a patron, the support it provides must have a significant impact on the client's capacity to advance its objectives; when the support does not reach this threshold, the international actor providing it qualifies as a mere supporter/sponsor³⁵. As for the number and type of patrons that a client could have, Biermann considers that there could be a master state patron which monopolises the support received by a given client, multiple state and even non-state actors as patrons exerting relatively comparable influence upon a client, and non-state actors as the sole patrons of a client³⁶.

Filling the gap in the research on the cessation by a patron state of its support towards a *de facto* state, Nina Caspersen and Sophie Gueudet argue that this disengagement could take the extreme form of complete abandonment or could be manifested moderately as a reduction of provided economic and military support³⁷. In case the patronage comes to an end, the dissolution of the *de facto* state almost invariably follows, and, if its military component diminishes, the existence of the *de facto*

state is significantly endangered. The change in patron policy could be brought about by the support becoming too costly, exceeding its capacities, or preventing the achievement of other objectives that have taken priority; the last determinant could reflect the fact that the patron state receives significantly more advantages in return for supporting the host state³⁸. To counter the inability or the unwillingness of the patron state to effectively act in this capacity, the *de facto* state client could try to convince that state's leadership to revert its approach, but it's also possible for it to enter into a patronage relationship with another state³⁹. It is to be observed that the abandonment on the part of the patron state almost inevitably leads to the termination of the frozen conflict when the *ad hoc* state cannot find an alternative state willing to assume its patronage. Under these circumstances, the host state is capable to forcefully reinstall its control over the *de facto* state and, thus, to effectively put an end to the frozen conflict; relying on Holsti's terminology, it could be said that the host state is in the position to resolve the conflict with the *de facto* state by means of military victory (conquest).

In the next section, the involvement of the Russian Federation in the frozen conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh will be considered within the theoretical framework provided by the patron-client relationship operating in the context of secessionist frozen conflicts.

The Russian Federation and the frozen conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh: a patron-client relationship analysis

The conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh, a region within the internationally recognised borders of Azerbaijan, generated high contention between Armenia and Azerbaijan even during the Soviet era and was later turned into a frozen conflict with the signing, in 1994, of a Russian mediated ceasefire that ended the First Karabakh War⁴⁰. The outcome of the conflict benefited the Armenian side which secured control of almost all the breakaway region and several surrounding

areas thus consolidating the position of the so-called Republic of Artsakh which emerged therein as a *de facto* state⁴¹. Armenia provided all-out support for this *de facto* state, which received economic and military assistance from Erevan, with the effect that its military reliance on Armenia became indispensable for its security; a patron-client relationship was thus forged, where patronage was provided by Armenia⁴². Following the dissolution of the Soviet Union, Armenia developed, in turn, a heavy economic and military dependence on the Russian Federation which reached the point where Armenia could no longer effectively defend itself without Moscow's involvement; the Russian Federation thus emerged as the patron of Armenia⁴³.

The 1994 ceasefire proved relatively stable until 27 September 2020, when the Second Karabakh War broke out; however, an episode of significant violence had taken place in 2016. After six weeks of fighting this second war terminated and, once again, the Russian Federation acted as a mediator for the conclusion of a ceasefire. Unlike in the previous war, Azerbaijan dominated the battlefield due to its superior capabilities developed with the help of Türkiye⁴⁴ and therefore the terms of the ceasefire brought clear advantage to it⁴⁵. Azeri forces obtained control over the seven districts around Nagorno-Karabakh and over parts of Nagorno-Karabakh⁴⁶. As for Armenia, it had to completely withdraw its forces and turn over to Azerbaijan the Lachin region that includes the Lachin Corridor as the main connection left between Armenia and the *de facto* state in Nagorno-Karabakh. According to the ceasefire, Russian peacekeepers, made up of 1,960 military personnel, had to provide free access through the Lachin Corridor and monitor compliance with the agreement along the contact line in Nagorno-Karabakh; the initial period for the deployment of these forces was five years but it was possible to be automatically renewed for another five years if none of the parties opposed. Under these new circumstances, the security of the *de facto* state ended up depending solely on the peacekeeping force deployed by the Russian Federation which thus became its patron state with respect to military matters⁴⁷. Armenia provided economic

support to the *de facto* state in Nagorno-Karabakh for whom it continued to maintain patronage relationships in the economic area⁴⁸.

Moreover, the 2020 ceasefire turned the frozen conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh to one resembling other frozen conflicts in the former Soviet space (Donbas, Transnistria, South Ossetia, Abkhazia) where the Russian Federation also supported *de facto* states; however, in the case of Nagorno-Karabakh, it did not create a *de facto* state but only assumed patronage of an already existing one⁴⁹. Confronted with the incapacity of Armenia to militarily protect Nagorno-Karabakh, the so-called Republic of Artsakh aimed at consolidating relations with the Russian Federation that it publicly designated as the only guarantor of its security. The self-proclaimed authorities of the *de facto* state cultivated relations with the Russian Federation by developing defence programmes in coordination with the peacekeeping contingent, emphasising cultural and social connections with the Russians, and even by considering a possible incorporation into the Russian Federation⁵⁰. In turn, Moscow's involvement extended beyond the military sphere to encompass humanitarian, infrastructure and political support, with the latter area of cooperation consisting of informal parliamentary contacts⁵¹.

The political relations of the *de facto* state with Erevan became tensioned in April 2022, when Erevan showed signs of flexibility with respect to the independence of Nagorno-Karabakh, and especially in May 2023, when the Prime Minister of Armenia, Nikol Pashinyan, announced that, as part of a mutual recognition of territorial integrity between Armenia and Azerbaijan, Armenia was willing to accept the sovereignty of Azerbaijan over Nagorno-Karabakh⁵².

The 2020 ceasefire was put under strain by the fighting which erupted in 2021 and 2022 but also by the blocking of the Lachin Corridor, which started in December 2022; in connection with this crisis, Russian peacekeepers have been criticised for their passive attitude which contravened their obligations under the terms of the 2020 ceasefire⁵³. When, on 19 September 2023, Azerbaijan launched its military operation against the remaining part

of the *de facto* state in Nagorno-Karabakh, Armenia demanded the Russian peacekeepers to intervene, but this did not happen⁵⁴. The overwhelming superiority of Azeri forces enabled them to take control of the whole of Nagorno-Karabakh and thus to terminate the functioning of the *de facto* state therein⁵⁵.

The conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh displays the core characteristics of the broad understanding of frozen conflicts that have been considered in the first section. More exactly, it emerged in the aftermath of the First Karabakh War, Azerbaijan and the *de facto* state from the breakaway region remained highly committed to their conflicting positions until the conflict terminated in 2023, the threat of renewed violence was always present and even erupted several times, and, finally, the Russian Federation, Armenia and Türkiye had been external powers that got involved in the conflict. With respect to the first characteristic, it is to be observed that the lifespan of the conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh included not only one, but two wars (First Karabakh War and Second Karabakh War), a situation which is not excluded by this characteristic, but which deviates from what could be considered its underlying assumption: armed conflict as only the beginning of a frozen conflict.

From the distinctive features of the narrow perspective on frozen conflicts, equally discussed within the previous section, it is present the feature that parties to it are a *de facto* state (the so-called Republic of Artsakh) and the state on whose territory that entity emerged (Azerbaijan). The support provided by external actors exclusively to the *de facto* state is an absent feature because the so-called Republic of Artsakh was backed by Armenia and later by the Russian Federation, while Azerbaijan also enjoyed the constant support of Türkiye.

It could be concluded that the conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh falls within the scope of the core elements that define frozen conflicts.

Considering the evolution of the frozen conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh from the point of view of one of the key constituents of the definition of frozen conflicts, namely the patron-client relationship, it is to be observed that Armenia is considered to have functioned as a patron state for the *de facto* state in that

region from 1994 to September 2023⁵⁶. Also, the Russian Federation, which is thought as operating in all this period as the patron state of Armenia⁵⁷, became equally the patron state for the *de facto* state in Nagorno-Karabakh following the entering into force of the 2020 ceasefire⁵⁸. Under the new circumstances arising from the 2020 ceasefire, the military security of the *de facto* state was no longer provided by Armenia but by the Russian Federation while Armenia remained the main source of economic support. Given the military dependence of Armenia on the Russian Federation since the 2020 ceasefire, Moscow acted as a direct patron for both Armenia and Nagorno-Karabakh. The changes at the level of patronage brought about by the 2020 ceasefire directed the efforts of the *de facto* state towards consolidating the replacement of Armenia with the Russian Federation as its security guarantor and towards gaining political support from Moscow for its territorial claims amid the wavering support of the Armenian government. Within the framework of the patron-client relationship, during the frozen conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh, Azerbaijan represented the host state in relation with the *de facto* state established in the breakaway region, while Türkiye is regarded by some scholars as gradually becoming the patron state of Azerbaijan⁵⁹.

The status of the Russian Federation as the patron of the *de facto* state of Nagorno-Karabakh plainly results from applying the four characteristics of the patron-client relationship identified by Biermann. With respect to the first one, the Russian Federation provided military security in return for the leverage it obtained in connection with both Armenia and Azerbaijan, but also with Türkiye that strongly backed the latter. Also, Russia was willing to assume patronage over Nagorno-Karabakh and the *de facto* state welcomed this arrangement as an adequate solution under pressing circumstances.

The second characteristic is present because the power of the Russian Federation far exceeded the power available to the *de facto* state, while the third characteristic is recognisable by the fact that the Russian Federation assumed obligations through the 2020 cease-

fire, but it was also active outside this formal framework by exploring political ties with the *de facto* state with the effect that the relationship was not a straightforward one. Finally, the 2020 ceasefire provided the possibility of the Russian peacekeeping forces to be maintained for ten years. It follows that the Russian Federation could not be regarded as a mere sponsor for the *de facto* state, to use the terms of Biermann, but clearly qualified as a patron for it. Relying on the typology of patrons advanced by Biermann, it could be said that the Nagorno-Karabakh case is illustrative for multiple state patronship because both Armenia and the Russian Federation acted as patrons for the *de facto* state; Moscow monopolised the military support, but the economic support rested mostly with Erevan.

The passive attitude of the Russian peacekeepers during the military operation undertaken by the Azeri forces in September 2023 represents the abandonment by a patron of its *de facto* state client, a dysfunctionality in the patron-client relationship that is ranked by Caspersen and Gueudet as the most extreme form of it on grounds of its devastating consequences on the existence of the *de facto* state. The explanation for the attitude of the Russian Federation should be looked for among the reasons leading up to the termination of a patron-client relationship at the initiative of the patron, namely becoming excessively costly, requiring capacities beyond those available, or standing in the way of far more important objectives.

Biermann argues that the position of the Russian Federation reflected its assessment that siding with Azerbaijan and implicitly with Türkiye, that is with the host state and its patron state, was clearly more advantageous⁶⁰. Caspersen and Gueudet consider that this re-orientation in Russian policy in South Caucasus mirrored geopolitical changes but equally reflected a reduction in the capacities of the Russian Federation⁶¹.

The shortage in the capacities of the Russian Federation to enforce the provisions of the 2020 ceasefire is often indicated as a reason for its decision not to interfere with the military operation conducted by Azeri forces. The weakness of the Russian Federation,

resulted from its setbacks in Ukraine, where the war was already going on for over a year, manifested in the military field but also in the area of international legitimacy. The Ukrainian front was absorbing most of Russian military resources, obliging Moscow to give it absolute priority, and, therefore, to engage its forces in South Caucasus would have exposed it to overstretching. In this line of reasoning, the collapse of the *de facto* state in Nagorno-Karabakh represented a rebalancing of power relations to the disadvantage of Russia that found itself bogged down in Ukraine⁶².

Another explanation provided for the acquiescence of the Russian Federation to the Azeri military operation was its deteriorating relations with Armenia which, under the Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan, had begun to consolidate relations with Western states⁶³. The cooperation with European Union was consolidated by the holding in January 2023 of the first meeting of the high-level Armenia–EU Political and Security Dialogue and the launch, in February 2023, of the European Union Mission in Armenia⁶⁴. The same year, accusing the inadequate reaction of the Collective Security Treaty Organization to the 2021 and 2022 breaches of the 2020 ceasefire, Armenia refused to allow the organisation to conduct an exercise on its territory, declined the nominalisation of a deputy head of the organisation and withdrew its representative to it⁶⁵. Also, just prior to the operation in Nagorno-Karabakh conducted by Azeri forces, the peacekeeping training exercise Eagle Partner took place in Armenia and involved military personnel from the United States⁶⁶. The link between the attitude of the Russian peacekeepers and the dissatisfaction of the Russian Federation with the foreign policy pursued by Armenia was made apparent by Dmitry Medvedev, the chairman of Russia's Security Council, who alluded, on 19 September, to the Armenia-NATO connections as a cause for the events in Nagorno-Karabakh⁶⁷. It is maintained that the Russian Federation intended to use the collapse of the *de facto* state from Nagorno-Karabakh as a trigger for the political collapse of Pashinyan government and subsequent access to power of politicians favourable to Russia⁶⁸; such an outcome was

highly useful for Moscow in context of the war in Ukraine. The abandonment of control over Nagorno-Karabakh was thus designed to exercise control over Armenia. It is relevant in this context the opinion that in 1994 the Russian Federation tipped the balance of the First Karabakh War in favour of Armenians because Azerbaijan, under president Abulfaz Elchibey, started in 1992 to orient its foreign policy towards the West, an approach which included the cultivation of close links with Türkiye, while distancing itself from Moscow through declining membership in the Community of Independent States (CIS) and advancing demands for the closure of Russian military bases on its territory⁶⁹. By trying to turn Armenia away from its pro-Western orientation, Moscow sided with Azerbaijan, Türkiye and Iran which were all concerned about Armenia strengthening relations with both the European Union and the United States⁷⁰.

A powerful determinant factor for the approach followed by the Russian Federation with respect to the termination of the frozen conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh is considered to be its growing economic dependence on Azerbaijan, resulting from international sanctions imposed to Moscow since February 2022⁷¹. Azerbaijan was indispensable for the completion of the International North-South Transit Corridor (INSTC) connecting the Russian Federation to the Persian Gulf by passing through Iran⁷². The prolongation of the war in Ukraine forced Russia to prioritise INSTC and in May 2023 it had concluded with Iran an important agreement on building the railroad component of this project. Moreover, the importance of Baku for Russian energy exports was equally enhanced against the background of mounting international pressure on the Russian Federation⁷³. The preference of the Russian Federation for Azerbaijan over Armenia cannot be separated from the *Declaration on Allied Cooperation between the Russian Federation and the Republic of Azerbaijan* signed in Moscow on 22 February 2022⁷⁴ and was latter mirrored by Vladimir Putin in the August 2024 state visit to Baku⁷⁵. The importance attributed by Russia to Azerbaijan was increased by the balancing of the latter between the interests of the Russian Federation and those of the West as proved by

the commitment of Baku to the territorial integrity of Ukraine⁷⁶ and the memorandum of understanding it signed on 18 July 2022 for exporting more gas to the European Union amidst its efforts to reduce energy dependence on Moscow⁷⁷. Moreover, another key leverage of Azerbaijan over Russia was the firm support it received on the part of Türkiye which, similar to Azerbaijan, developed a balancing position within the context of the war in Ukraine and thus provided Moscow with the much-needed economic opportunities and diplomatic mediation⁷⁸.

It follows that the Russian Federation was determined to allow the carrying out of the Azeri military operation from September 2023 by a combination of two types of factors arising from its involvement in the war in Ukraine: the reduction of its military capacities and the prevalence of the interest to develop its economic cooperation with Azerbaijan, to consolidate economic and diplomatic relations with Türkiye as supporter of Azerbaijan, and to hinder the Euro-Atlantic integration of Armenia as a means to maintain a significant influence over it. These considerations correspond to the causes underpinning the abandonment of a *de facto* client state by its patron.

Conclusions

The conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh falls under the definition of frozen conflicts and its termination conforms to the functioning of the patron-client relationship within the context of a frozen conflict involving a *de facto* secessionist state. In the general terms of the patron-client relationship, the end to this frozen conflict could be described as follows: the patron state that provides military security to a *de facto* state established on the territory of a host state decides to cease patronage relations and the host state takes advantage of the vulnerability of the *de facto* state and resolves the conflict by completely defeating it militarily. Equally within the framework of the patron-client relationship, the abandonment by the Russian Federation of its client from Nagorno-Karabakh finds this general explanation: the patron state of a *de facto* secessionist state involved in a frozen

conflict finds it more difficult to direct military resources towards protecting its client, obtains greater economic and political advantages from siding with the host state and its most important international supporter, and has a really dysfunctional relationship with the state that acts as the other patron for the *de facto* state. Taking into account these considerations, it could be suggested that the remaining frozen conflicts around the Black Sea could be expected to terminate by a combination of two factors that are likely to bear significant influence on the Russian Federation's decision to cease supporting the *de facto* states involved in these conflicts: a substantial decrease of the Russian military power and a significant degree of economic and political dependence on the host state and its most supportive international actors. When these factors are simultaneously present, they are not necessarily conducive to a violent resolution of these frozen conflicts so that ending them peacefully remains a possibility. Moreover, the precedent set by the conclusion of the frozen conflict in Nagorno-Karabakh could contribute to ending all frozen conflicts in the vicinity of the Black Sea which, therefore, are not to be regarded as virtually irresolvable.

Notes

¹ Dan Dungaciu, Jakub M. Godzimirski, *Russia and Frozen Conflicts in the Black Sea Region*. Flanks Policy Brief, pp. 6-7, New Strategy Center, The Norwegian Institute of International Affairs, 2020, <https://www.newstrategycenter.ro/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/FLANKS-Policy-Brief-Russia-and-Frozen-Conflicts-in-the-Black-Sea-Region.pdf>, 12.02.2025. On the existence of a frozen conflict in Donbas see Dominique Arel, Jesse Driscoll, *Ukraine's Unnamed War: Before the Russian Invasion of 2022*, chapter 8, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2023 and Jan Ludvik, Vojtech Bahensky, *The Russia-Ukraine frozen conflict: Evidence from an expert survey*, *Comparative Strategy*, vol. 43, no. 2, 2024, pp. 104–117, <https://doi.org/10.1080/01495933.2024.2317250>.

² Michal Smetana, Jan Ludvik, *Between war and peace: a dynamic reconceptualization of frozen conflicts*, p. 3, *Asia Europe Journal*, vol. 17, no. 4, 2019, pp. 1–14, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10308-018-0521-x> and Adriana Cuppuleri, *Russia and Frozen Conflicts in the Post-Soviet Space*, pp. 1331-1332 in Oliver P. Richmond, Gezim Visoka (eds.), *The Palgrave Encyclopedia of Peace and Conflict Studies*, Cham, Palgrave Macmillan, 2022.

³ Thomas D. Grant, *Frozen Conflicts and International Law*, Cornell International Law Journal, pp. 363-364, vol. 50, no. 3, 2017, pp. 361-413.

⁴ Thomas D. Grant, *op. cit.*, pp. 363-364 and Michal Smetana, Jan Ludvik, *op. cit.*, p. 1, 2.

⁵ Dan Dungaciu, Jakub M. Godzimirski, *op. cit.*, p. 4.

⁶ K. J. Holsti, *Resolving International Conflicts: A Taxonomy of Behavior and Some Figures on Procedures*, pp. 272-274, *The Journal of Conflict Resolution*, vol. 10, no. 3, 1966, pp. 272-296.

⁷ *Ibidem*, pp. 281-282. One could observe that Holsti puts the term of passive settlement between quotation marks which means that he considered it to have only an informal use in that period.

⁸ *Ibidem*, p. 283.

⁹ *Ibidem*, p. 273.

¹⁰ Michal Smetana, Jan Ludvik, *op. cit.*, pp. 3, 4 and Adriana Cuppuleri, *op. cit.*, p. 1332.

¹¹ Michal Smetana, Jan Ludvik, *op. cit.*, pp. 3, 4.

¹² Valery Perry, *At Cross Purposes? Democratization and Peace Implementation Strategies in Bosnia and Herzegovina's Frozen Conflict*, p. 36, *Human Rights Review*, vol. 10, no. 1, 2009, pp. 35-54, DOI 10.1007/s12142-008-0090-2.

¹³ Michal Smetana, Jan Ludvik, *op. cit.*, p. 4.

¹⁴ *Ibidem*, p. 6.

¹⁵ Adriana Cuppuleri, *op. cit.*, pp. 1331, 1332.

¹⁶ *Ibidem*, p. 1332.

¹⁷ Michal Smetana, Jan Ludvik, *op. cit.*, p. 2, Adriana Cuppuleri, *op. cit.*, p. 1332. See also Lucie Konečná, *Modern Frozen Conflicts: Conditions for the Occurrence of the Phenomenon*, p. 4, Obrana a strategie, no. 2, 2022, pp. 3-18, DOI:10.3849/1802-7199.22.2022.02.003-018 ("According to some scientists, the notion of frozenness may imply (...) that such conflicts appear only in the post-Soviet space.")

¹⁸ Valery Perry, *op. cit.*, p. 36.

¹⁹ Bezen Balamir Coskun, *Resolving the Conflict Between Serbia and Kosovo: Can Turkey Act as a Mediator?* pp. 297, 298 in Branislav Radeljić, Mustafa Cüneyt Özşahin (eds.), *Turkey's Return to the Western Balkans: Policies of Continuity and Transformation*, Cham, Springer, 2022 and Anton Bebler, *The Serbia-Kosovo conflict* in Anton Bebler (ed.), *Frozen conflicts in Europe*, Verlag Barbara Budrich, 2015.

²⁰ Anton Bebler, *Introduction*, p. 1, in Anton Bebler (ed.), *Frozen conflicts*, Europe, Opladen, Verlag Barbara Budrich, 2015.

²¹ Carolina Chavez Fregoso, Nikola Zivkovic, *Western Sahara: a frozen conflict*, *Journal of Regional Security*, vol. 7, no. 2, 2012, pp. 139-150, DOI: 10.11643/issn.2217-995X122SPZ21.

²² Mona Yacoubian, *Syria's Frozen Conflict Heats Up*, 3 December 2024, United States Institute for Peace, <https://www.usip.org/publications/2024/12/syrias-frozen-conflict-heats>, 22.01.2025.

²³ Adriana Cuppuleri, *op. cit.*, p. 1331, Stefano Felician, *North and South Korea: a frozen conflict on the verge of unfreezing?* Istituto Affari Internazionali Working Papers 11/24, 2011, https://ciaotest.cc.columbia.edu/wps/iai/0023128/f_0023128_18918.pdf, 13.01.2025.

²⁴ Lucie Konečná, *op. cit.*, p. 5.

²⁵ Kamil Christoph Klosek, Vojtěch Bahenský, Michal Smetana, Jan Ludvik, *Frozen conflicts in world politics: A new dataset*, figure 2, *Journal of Peace Research*, vol. 58, no. 4, 2021, pp. 849-858, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022343320929726>.

²⁶ Thomas D. Grant, *op. cit.*, pp. 390-397.

²⁷ See, for example, Selim Kurt and Gökürk Tuysuzoglu who consider that both the First and the Second Karabakh War are part of the frozen conflict from Nagorno-Karabakh (See Selim Kurt, Gökürk Tuysuzoglu, *Is Nagorno-Karabakh no longer a frozen conflict zone after the 2020 war?* pp. 53, 54, *International Journal*, vol. 78, no. 1-2, 2023, pp. 41-59, DOI: 10.1177/00207020231179048).

²⁸ Filon Morar, *The Myth of 'Frozen conflicts': transcending illusive Dilemmas*, p. 11, *Per Concordiam*, vol. 1, no. 2, 2018, https://www.marshallcenter.org/sites/default/files/files/2020-06/pC_V1N2_en.pdf, 11.03.2025, Sergiu Mitrescu, Andrei Pavel, *Frozen Conflicts in the Heat of War. The Changing Tide in the Black Sea Region*, pp. 6, 7, New Strategy Center, Bucharest, 2023, <https://news-strategycenter.ro/en/nsc-study-frozen-conflicts-in-the-heat-of-war-the-changing-tide-in-the-black-sea-region/>, 15.03.2025, Dov Lynch, *New thinking about 'frozen' conflicts*, p. 192, *Helsinki Monitor*, vol. 16, no. 3, 2005, pp. 192-195, Laurence Broers, *From "frozen conflict" to enduring rivalry: reassessing the Nagorny Karabakh conflict*, p. 557, *Nationalities Papers*, vol. 43, no. 4, 2015, pp. 556-576.

²⁹ Dov Lynch, *op. cit.*, p. 192.

³⁰ The state on whose territory the secessionist conflict takes place is called parent state but also host state. Given that the term *parent state* implies an emotional connection that is not necessarily present (see Rafael Biermann, *Patron-client relations in secessionist conflict: introducing the special issue*, note 1, *Territory, Politics, Governance*, vol. 13, no. 1, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.1080/21622671.2024.2410236>, 24.01.2025), I consider that *host state* is a more adequate term to describe the complex nature of the relationship between a *de facto* state and the state it strives to secede from.

³¹ Dan Dungaciu, Jakub M. Godzimirski, *op. cit.*, pp. 4, 5.

³² Rafael Biermann, *op. cit.*, p. 2.

³³ For this latter deficiency see Rafael Biermann, *Conceptualising patron-client relations in secessionist conflict. A research agenda*, pp. 18, 21, *Territory, Politics, Governance*, vol. 13, no. 1, 2025, pp. 9-27, <https://doi.org/10.1080/21622671.2024.2318467> and Nina Caspersen, Sophie Guedet, *No longer what you used to be: Renegotiating relations between de facto states and their patrons*, p. 179, *European Journal of International Relations*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 178-202, 2025 doi.org/10.1177/13540661241295690. Caspersen and Guedet indicate that the failing of a patron state to respect its commitment of support towards a *de facto* state is generally not considered through the lens of the patron-client relationship approach because this approach is usually used to analyse dysfunctions between full-fledged states engaged in such hierarchical interaction.

³⁴ Rafael Biermann, *Conceptualising patron-client relations in secessionist conflict. A research agenda*, pp. 11, 13.

³⁵ *Ibidem*, p. 15.

³⁶ *Ibidem*, pp. 14, 15.

³⁷ Nina Caspersen, Sophie Gueudet, *op. cit.*, p. 183.

³⁸ *Ibidem*, p.183. Rafael Biermann, *Conceptualising patron-client relations in secessionist conflict. A research agenda*, p. 21.

³⁹ Nina Caspersen, Sophie Gueudet, *op. cit.*, p. 184.

⁴⁰ The First Karabakh War began in 1988 but started to be fought on a large scale in 1991 when Nagorno-Karabakh declared its independence from Azerbaijan (See Walter Landgraf, Nareg Seferian, *A "Frozen Conflict" Boils Over: Nagorno-Karabakh in 2023 and Future Implications*, January 2024, <https://www.fpri.org/article/2024/01/a-frozen-conflict-boils-over-nagorno-karabakh-in-2023-and-future-implications/>, 18.12.2024).

⁴¹ Sergiu Mitrescu, Andrei Pavel, *op. cit.*, p. 9, International Crisis Group, *The Nagorno-Karabakh Conflict: A Visual Explainer*, <https://www.crisisgroup.org/content/nagorno-karabakh-conflict-visual-explainer>, 23.01.2025.

⁴² Nina Caspersen, Sophie Gueudet, *op. cit.*, p. 9, Thomas de Waal, *Armenia Navigates a Path Away From Russia*, July 11, 2024, <https://carnegieendowment.org/research/2024/07/armenia-navigates-a-path-away-from-russia?lang=en>, 15.11.2024.

⁴³ Thomas de Waal, *op. cit.*, and Eva Hartog, *Russia shrugs as Azerbaijan attacks Nagorno-Karabakh*, 20 September 2023, <https://www.politico.eu/article/while-azerbaijan-attacks-nagorno-karabakh-moscow-leans-back/>, 22.01.2025, Nina Caspersen, Sophie Gueudet, *op. cit.*, p. 190.

⁴⁴ Galina M. Yemelianova, *The De Facto State of Nagorno-Karabakh: Historical and Geopolitical Perspectives*, p. 1355, *Europe-Asia Studies*, vol. 75, no. 8, October 2023, pp. 1336-1359.

⁴⁵ Sergiu Mitrescu, Andrei Pavel, *op. cit.*, p. 9. For the text of the agreement see *Statement by the Prime Minister of the Republic of Armenia, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the President of the Russian Federation*, 10.11.2020, <https://peacemaker.un.org/sites/default/files/document/files/2024/05/statement20by20azerbaijan20armenia20and20russia.pdf>, 22.01.2025.

⁴⁶ Alexa Fults, Paul Stronski, *The Ukraine War Is Reshaping the Armenia-Azerbaijan Conflict*, 25 April 2022, <https://carnegieendowment.org/posts/2022/04/the-ukraine-war-is-reshaping-the-armenia-azerbaijan-conflict?lang=en>, 13.02.2025.

⁴⁷ Nina Caspersen, Sophie Gueudet, *op. cit.*, pp. 187, 190.

⁴⁸ *Ibidem*, pp. 194, 195.

⁴⁹ Vladimir Socor, *Russia's Karabakh Protectorate Taking Clearer Shape* (Part Two), *Eurasia Daily Monitor*, vol. 18, no. 46, 22 March 2021, <https://jamestown.org/program/russias-karabakh-protectorate-taking-clearer-shape-part-two/>, 09.12.2024.

⁵⁰ Nina Caspersen, Sophie Gueudet, *op. cit.*, pp. 190, 191.

⁵¹ *Ibidem*, p. 190, Vladimir Socor, *op. cit.*

⁵² Nina Caspersen, Sophie Gueudet, *op. cit.*, p. 187, Ani Mejlumyan, *Officials in Karabakh break with Armenia over negotiations*, 15 April 2022, <https://eurasianet.org/>

officials-in-karabakh-break-with-armenia-over-negotiations, 22.01.2025.

⁵³ Claire Mills, *What is happening in Nagorno-Karabakh?* pp. 6, 7, Research Briefing Number 9862, 28 September 2023, <https://researchbriefings.files.parliament.uk/documents/CBP-9862/CBP-9862.pdf>, 11.01.2025 and Walter Landgraf, Nareg Seferian, *op. cit.*

⁵⁴ Katarzyna Chawryło, Miłosz Bartosiewicz, *Russia seals the demise of Nagorno-Karabakh*, 05 October 2023, <https://www.osw.waw.pl/en/publikacje/analyses/2023-10-05/russia-seals-demise-nagorno-karabakh>, 08.01.2025 and Eva Hartog, *op. cit.*

⁵⁵ Walter Landgraf, Nareg Seferian, *op. cit.*

⁵⁶ Nina Caspersen, Sophie Gueudet, *op. cit.*, pp. 186, 187.

⁵⁷ *Ibidem*, p. 190.

⁵⁸ *Ibidem*, pp. 190, 191 and Rafael Biermann, *Patron-client relations in secessionist conflict: introducing the special issue*, p. 3.

⁵⁹ Rafael Biermann, *Patron-client relations in secessionist conflict: introducing the special issue*, p. 3.

⁶⁰ Rafael Biermann, *Conceptualising patron-client relations in secessionist conflict. A research agenda*, p. 21.

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⁶⁴ European External Action Service, *EU Mission in Armenia*, https://www.eeas.europa.eu/euma_en?s=41_02_83.

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⁶⁹ Zaur Shiriyev, *Azerbaijan's Relations with Russia. Closer by Default?*, pp. 6, 7, Chatham House. The Royal Institute of International Affairs, Research Paper, March 2019, <https://www.chathamhouse.org/sites/default/files/2019-03-14-Azerbaijan2.pdf>, 19.02.2025.

⁷⁰ The shared preoccupation of the four states towards an increased level of EU and US involvement in Armenia took the form of almost similar statements issued by those states following the EU-US-Armenia high-level meeting in support of the Republic of Armenia's resilience that took place on 5 April 2024 in Brussels (See Republic of Türkiye, Ministry of Foreign Affairs, No. 55, 4 April 2024, Regarding the Trilateral Meeting Between Armenia, the USA and the EU to be Held in Brussels on 5 April 2024, 5 April 2024, https://www.mfa.gov.tr/no_-55_-ermenistan-abd-ve-ab-arasinda-5-nisan-2024-tarihinde-bruksel-de-duzenlenecek-uclu-toplantı-hk.en.mfa; The Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Russian Federation, Foreign Ministry statement in connection with the high-level Armenia-US-EU format meeting, 5 April 2024, https://mid.ru/en/foreign_policy/news/1942789/; Republic of Azerbaijan, Ministry of Foreign Affairs, No. 136/24, Response by Aykhan Hajizada, MFA Spokesperson, to the media inquiry on a joint EU-Armenia-US conference to be held on 5 April 2024 in Brussels, <https://www.mfa.gov.az/en/news/no13624>; Islamic Republic of Iran, Ministry of Foreign Affairs, <https://en.mfa.ir/portal/newsview/743174/Kanaani-urges-regional-cooperation-for-peace-in-Caucasus>).

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